

Products loved by users: developing a tool to assist designers' awareness of user emotional responses to products

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Theme: Attachment and behaviour

Abstract

Some products appear to generate strong emotional responses amongst particular user groups. The phrases 'love it' and 'hate it' can often be heard. As design is becoming less about products and more about designing user experience, it becomes more important than ever that designers are sensitive and aware of user experiences. Developing empathy is proving to be a valuable element in supporting more effective design outcomes.

This paper explores such emotional responses in a sample of first year industrial design undergraduates from the UK. Students were required to work in small groups and identify a product they agreed they 'loved' and one that they 'hated'. Each group then employed brainstorming techniques to explore why they responded that way in terms of the specific features or aspects of products. The pooled results were collected and evaluated. In addition a focus group discussion was conducted to explore these students' views on the relationship of design and emotion.

For this study, 'love it' responses to products provide the focus of this paper. Patterns were identified and a comparison made between the two sets of qualitative data. In this way the authors intend to work towards building a form of 'checklist' of 'buttons to press' design cues, design triggers.... when designing. This will, of course need to be related to the practice of teaching and learning of design. Whilst it is appreciated that effective design cannot be distilled into a checklist it is hoped that such a list may represent a useful design tool.

Introduction

The importance of the emotional dimension in the user/product relationships is becoming well established (Koskinen *et al* 2005, Chapman 2005). The term supra-functionality has been used to highlight the emotional dimension of product use and ownership which include; the social, aspirational, cultural, tribal and even spiritual needs of the users (Weightman & McDonagh 2003). A truly 'successful' product offers a balance of both functionality and supra-functionality (Weightman and McDonagh 2002, Watson and McDonagh 2003). Van Hinte (1997) concurs: "Owning tangible things is an undeniable human need. Products provide symbols of identity to their users and the people around them. They carry meaning and are constant reminders of who we are, where we are, our activities, our history and our future."

This paper is based on an existing teaching and learning exercise which engaged a group of first year industrial design undergraduate students in the UK. This exercise encourages students to explore the emotional dimension of design; specifically the aspects of products that generate emotional responses (e.g. "love it"). That is to say attempting to encourage students to evaluate why *they* react in an emotional way to specific products. Such an activity provides opportunities for design students to externalise their feelings and articulate complex emotional responses to products (visual stimuli etc.) sometimes for the first time. This work is based on empirical findings that highlighted that a large majority of these new undergraduates had not been required to consider the nature of design and emotion prior to joining the university (McDonagh and Denton 2005). This had resulted in design educators exploring innovative ways of developing this dimension of student design work. The long term aim is to explore whether it is possible to develop a design 'tool' which will enable undergraduate designers to consider the emotional need and, particularly to be able to do so in a manner which is sensitive to users in socio-economic groups other than the designers themselves. It is acknowledged that this cannot be done on a 'check list' basis but needs careful integration within the practice of teaching and learning at an undergraduate level.

This paper reports the initial stages of this process by, firstly, describing some of the basic background reading in this emerging field. Secondly the teaching exercise used as a basis for data collection is reported. The data is then evaluated and discussed in relation to the practice of teaching and learning design at an undergraduate level. Conclusions are drawn and

suggestions made for directions that could be used to develop a design tool to assist undergraduates in developing an awareness of and sensitivity to the emotional dimensions of user reactions to products. This is an area that is important for effective design but one which is difficult for many undergraduates to grasp.

Background

Breen *et al* (2004) interviewed a number of 'Masters of Design', that is experienced design practitioners, on how they perceive design developing in the business world. There were a number of messages, but amongst them was that design must be emotional and that products must make emotional connections with customers. McDonagh and Formosa (2004) reported a survey by Smart Design. This indicated that users' satisfaction with a product was extremely dependent on them forming an emotional connection with that product. They further reported that critical factors were that the product should exceeded expectations, surprise with performance and create a happy experience. Here we see the centrality of functionality being assumed, but above this, a more emotional experience demanded. Similarly Chapman (2005: 24) called for design to cater 'for deeper; more profound and poetic human needs, taking users beyond the ephemeral world of techno centric design toward a rich, interactive domain of emotionally durable objects and experiences'. Again we see the assumption of technical effectiveness, but a plea for more: the emotional dimension to products.

One way of designers managing to gain a perspective on users emotional needs in products is to involve users within the designing process: an area of on-going debate since the 1960s in various forms. Users can become significantly and actively involved on two levels. Firstly, they can provide a central focus for the designer (User-Centred Design, Human-Centred Design, Universal Design and Inclusive Design). Secondly, they can become active participants within the designing process (Participatory Design)(Luck 2003). Participation within the designing process can ensure more user-designer contact, resulting in more authentic insights.

Reich *et al* (1996) found that:

Participatory design was considered the antithesis of traditional design in

which designers are expected to exhibit their expertise... An assumption of traditional design is that active user involvement comes after the design process is over... In traditional design, participation is often side-stepped by reducing the user to a databank.

Involving users within the designing process has can be beneficial, but real collaborative engagement can offer more insight, shared understanding and develop empathy between all parties. However, user involvement within the designing process is now recognised and valued as a dynamic on going activity (Reich *et al* 1996).

Emotion and Teaching and Learning at an undergraduate level

Denton (2002) had previously found strong indications that the consideration of emotional aspects to design work was new to a group of industrial design undergraduate students on entry to the university; indeed they found this a significant mind shift. Prior to university these students, on the whole, were not explicitly encouraged by teachers to respond emotionally to project work nor had they discussed this dimension with teachers or amongst themselves. This finding was from a small sample and of students from an industrial design course with a significant technological element. It could not be extrapolated to students on courses following other forms of design. However, this finding correlates with others by this author (Denton 2005) that design teaching at a schools level in the UK had become extremely formulaic. Teachers are increasingly 'teaching to the test', that is developing a ritualistic, linear and inflexible design approach which focuses on the production of attractive folios. In practice design tasks are often 'wicked' (Rittel 1973) in that as we work on them our understanding of their nature changes; inflexible design approaches cannot accommodate such phenomenon. Having been taught a linear, inflexible design approach at a schools level must have an impact on the teaching and learning of emotion and design on undergraduate design orientated degree courses. This may contribute to students chasing grades rather than focusing on the journey/experience of their degree programme.

Method

Data was gathered using a group brainstorming exercise. The sample comprised of a group of 130 first year undergraduate industrial designers divided into thirty two subgroups of four. The group were relatively homogeneous, of average age 18/19, from the UK with only a few

exceptions, and a female/male ratio of approximately 1:4. It should be noted that this cohort was in its first year at university and that all but a few had been educated through UK schools. Discussion with the group on experiences in design at a school level prior to joining the university had revealed that only a few schools had raised the issue of design and emotion. The majority of the student group had been surprised to find that the issue had been raised in their first year undergraduate design practice exercises.

The method was based on a teaching and learning exercise conducted in three steps and designed to help students explore the emotional relationship between user and product. The first exercise was a self-contained: acting as individuals the students were asked to brainstorm products they 'loved', that is had a positive emotional relationship and include images and notes exploring this emotional dimension (refer to Figure A). They were asked to respond viscerally rather than try to logically evaluate their decisions.

Figure A: Brainstorm by an individual on a product they 'love' – Zenoa eraser

The second step placed individuals into sub-groups of four and asked the sub-groups to identify one product they could agree on as likely to cause a positive emotional reaction with the user, in this case themselves. They were then asked to produce a sheet with an image of the item and to brainstorm why they felt the way they did (refer to Figure B).

Figure B: Brainstorm by group on agreed product - G5 Apple computer

This exercise then led into a third phase where students attempted a paper based re-design of an existing product to build in an improved emotional relationship with a user. This paper, however, is based on the results of the second part of the exercise: the data generated by thirty two sub-groups of four students. The sheets from each sub-group were collected and the authors developed a summary sheet of points and products. The authors then attempted to identify natural clusters emerging by a simple process of direct comparison. For example, it was possible to extract clusters for: function, aesthetics (line, colour, surface texture), novelty, ergonomics, character, ecological impression, identity (logo) and miscellaneous. Under each of these headings were grouped points from each sub-group's sheet.

The method employed was, to a large extent opportunistic in that the exercise was used as a part of the teaching of design practice in the first year of the programme; the aim being to begin to sensitise students to the issue of users developing an emotional response to some products. It is anticipated that emotional responses to products may be highly individual and based on complex and dynamic factors. In addition the method used to identify the clusters and allocate the content in this exercise was subjective. Having said that, there is no intention to attempt to extrapolate these findings beyond this, specific, group. Indeed it is acknowledged that had groupings been re-arranged a different set of products may have emerged. Nevertheless, as a scoping exercise, the size of the group is such that a reasonable set of factors have emerged. Further work would be needed to gain a more reliable perspective on this particular socio/economic/cultural group's responses to the exercise or, indeed to open it further to other groups. To some extent this could be achieved by triangulated exercises and using factor analysis to identify, statistically, the most probable

clusters. From this could come an attempt to quantify the range and strength of specific responses.

Results

function

portability, folding, compact
flexible in use, multifunctional,
versatile, performs task well
out performs others,
easy to use, few operating buttons,
attention to detail, quiet,
variety in same product

line

alignment, angular,
symmetry/asymmetry,
elegant/graceful, quality finish,
uncluttered/clean lines,
simple forms/minimalist,
flowing form, curves = 'life',
smooth/sleek

character

humanoid or 'face',
cute, cheeky,
movements,
robotic movement,
gender flexible or overtly
masculine or feminine

ergonomics

obvious how to use,
form/colour/texture guides
how to hold,
just sits in the hand,
buttons easy to find
universal for left and right hand,
clarity of display

colour

bright/primary/contrast,
red = bold, silver = style,
blue = refreshing/water
yellow = technical,
matt black = classy
white = hygiene
colour complements task

identity (logo)

identifiable, iconic,
limited availability = desirable,
nationalistic,
professional,
known for quality,
expensive seen as positive,
product evolves

novelty

unique/different,
technically advanced,
interesting sound/surprise,
'alive' - reacts to you,
customisable/personalised

texture

shiny /smooth,
grip/rubbery/soft buttons,
soft touch/range of textures

ecological

recyclable

miscellaneous

nostalgia/retro,
encourages fiddling,
buttons discreet

Table A. Factors identified from group 'love it' brainstorm

The factors listed were simply (or directly) gathered and recorded from the brainstorm sheets of separate sub-groups of four students. The specific product being referred to was not the central issue and is not reported in the table, though some are referred to in the text where appropriate. The focus of this discussion is the factors that were identified as contributing to the group's positive reaction.

There are apparent disagreements within the results. For example some groups perceived angularity in a specific product as a positive, whereas other groups admired a different product for its curves. This is not necessarily a contradiction, but a contextual issue and demonstrates the danger of extrapolating reported responses beyond the specific context they refer to. Further work could gain more broadly reliable feedback on specific products and establish the range of responses more effectively for this age/culture group.

There were a number of categories that the researchers saw emerging: function, aesthetic (line, colour, texture), ergonomics, novelty, character, identity, ecological and miscellaneous.

Discussion: factors relating to an emotional response of user to product

... these physical objects serve a deeper and altogether more profound purpose that is frequently overlooked; consumable objects and experiences provide a means for us of engaging with the world on both rational and emotional levels.
(Chapman 2005, p19)

Whilst no attempt was made within the exercise to quantify the responses, it was clear that the largest category was that of **functionality**. In many respects the factors listed are relatively predictable, but they do illustrate the centrality of good function for this group. Products which were reported as causing an emotional bond were frequently termed as ‘out-performing similar products’ or offering extra functionality such as versatility and flexibility. McDonagh and Formosa (2004) have supported this view noting that their work with ‘masters of design’ showed these designers felt products needed to exceed expectations and surprise with performance. We have reached a point where functionality is assumed; the product will be fully functional in its role, but if a user is to gain a more emotional benefit from using a product it appears to need to offer more functionality. One example given was “better portability; perhaps by folding or compacting in some way”. Many modern mobile phones illustrate this well: compact in carry mode, but able to open up enabling easier ergonomics and a larger, clearer screen. Similarly improved flexibility or multi-functionality were valued by this student group as illustrated by modern multiple use communications devices combining phone, camera, data sources, entertainment etc.

Multi-functionality, however, often can mean complexity of controls. The data showed that ease of use and minimal controls were important factors in making a product 'loved'. Examples given which illustrate this were the iPod with its simple central control wheel. This product also illustrates the factor of **variety** in the same product: effectively the ability to stand out from the crowd. This was also illustrated by the classic Zippo lighter, which can be customised with different graphics. We should also note the importance of functionality having an element of surprise or delight in use. Designers can design a product to operate in a certain way, for example a DVD carrier opening, but to develop real user reaction this simple operation should be done in a surprising, delightful manner.

Aesthetics factors were also frequently reported. They have been categorised by the authors into: line, colour and texture. Simple forms with clean lines were valued. iPod and Apple Mac computers were often used as the reference for these factors. Interestingly both symmetry and asymmetry were valued in specific contexts. Automotive design was mainly used to illustrate these factors, for example the symmetry in a car such as the Mini, but also asymmetry in the form of some car instrumentation/dash board areas. Asymmetry may also be linked to the category established as 'novelty' as products employing this technique as an aesthetic often stood out as different to similar products which relied on symmetry. Both approaches can work to enhance product desirability, but context remains important.

The student group valued simple, minimalist, uncluttered forms on the whole. These used clean lines and smooth flowing form. Students reported appreciating forms with these qualities as 'sleek', 'elegant', and 'graceful'.

Colour was often reported as a factor which encouraged attachment to a product. The students concerned did not appear to favour a particular colour, but reported specific colours as communicating particular qualities, as indicated in the table above, for example matt black equated to 'classy' for them. Bright, strong colours appeared to predominate in preferences. In addition the use of contrasting colours appeared to contribute to the sense of attachment such as in the Zenoa eraser (refer to Figure A) or the range of Alessi kitchen products. Colour was also appreciated where it was used as fine detail, often in contrast with a subdued background for purposes such as indicating a button or control (action zone).

Texture was classified by the authors as an aesthetic factor, though there were degrees of

functionality, such as improved grip or improved tactile quality, for example a 'soft' or 'rubbery' grip was frequently referred to in conjunction with these products. Contrast was often used by the designers of these products in terms of smooth and shiny surfaces for the bulk of the product juxtaposed with soft buttons using elastomer surfaces. A range of textures appeared to offer the user variety and a wider tactile experience.

The students frequently referred to the quality of **ergonomics** in these products. The use of form, colour and texture by the designer could guide the user in holding the product. The best products needed minimal indications of how to hold and use them; the fingers were guided to buttons by careful ergonomics underlying form. Texture could aid grip and enable less force to be used to hold the product, making them easier and more pleasant to handle for longer periods of time. Texture can also help the user navigate the product. Other ergonomics factors appreciated in these products included simple and clear displays/sight lines and a degree of universality for left and right-handed users.

Products which appeared to offer a '**character**' were appreciated. Factors such as the product having humanoid features (VW Beetle), particularly facial, were considered 'cute', 'cheeky'. Some students reported an impression of an overt gender effect to be positive, yet being attractive to both genders was also reported positively. Products with parts which moved were often referred to as having character, particularly where that movement was surprising (also links to novelty).

A product '**identity**' was sometimes associated with a well known brand and logo. This has similarity to character but was seen much more specifically as relating to acknowledged quality in that brand. Terms used included 'iconic', 'professional' and 'identifiable'. Associated with these were that the product was known for its expense and limited availability. Some students pointed out specific nationalistic icons, such as the Mini (UK), but also the VW (Germany) or Lamborghini (Italy). Surprisingly students appreciated a strong nationalistic character, even when different to their own nationality.

Novelty emerged as a strong indicator of products which were appreciated, particularly where there was an element of surprise in the way the product operated. The students appeared to desire products which are different in some distinguishable way. This could be by working in a different way (Rabbit cork extractor), be technically in advance of similar products or be customisable. Surprise was highly appreciated in relation to functionality, form and the way in that the product operates. Sounds could

enhance this effect. Some products were perceived as almost 'alive' in the way they interact with the user.

One group put forward the Smart Car as a 'loved' product and pointed out that its **ecological** footprint was far better than other cars. Other groups pointed out that some other products they had selected were recyclable. Clearly there was an awareness of ecological issues, though these did not feature strongly in the range of products identified in the exercise, which surprised the authors.

A number of features were identifiable under '**miscellaneous**'. A number of nostalgia based products included the old mini, VW Beetle and the Zippo lighter. This is interesting as the age range of the student group precludes them being drivers when the original cars were in production. It would appear that any nostalgia is for some form of image of the period rather than personal experience.

One other factor which was evident from the student sheets was that some 'loved' products were ones which the students reported 'encouraged fiddling', i.e. objects which one can continually manipulate and which may offer some form of comfort. Examples were often relatively simple such as the Zenoa eraser which is enclosed in a case which rotates to protect the eraser surface.

Discussion:

teaching and learning in relation to appreciating emotion and design

This work and others (McDonagh and Denton 2005) demonstrate that, within this sample, the students had had little prior experience of appreciating the need to design for the emotional relationship between user and product. The exercise reported was the first used in the first year to start to open students' minds to the issue. Linked closely to this is the issue of enabling student designers to design for socio/economic/cultural groups beyond their own. This raises the need to be able to empathise with such disparate groups, rather than simply understanding the direct ergonomics of specific groups. According to Hoffman (2000), empathy is "[the] effective response more appropriate to someone else's situation than one's own.". Plowman (2003) professes that empathy is "the altered subjectivity that can come from immersion into a particular context," a view that is helpful for designers learning about human communication during the design process. Fulton Suri (2003) also believes that empathy "... is simply about achieving greater awareness, an extended imagination and sensitivity to another person's world in a powerfully memorable way."

Students need to be taught empathic research methods. Koskinen (2003) notes these are inherently user-centred. A positive outcome of empathic design research approaches is that it can allow for recognition of both functional and supra-functional needs such as the emotional dimension.

Conclusion

The exercise reported has been conducted for several years and has proven to encourage students to select a product and gently introduce the evaluation of products. For some students this has literally been the first opportunity they may have to externalise and articulate their feelings and emotional responses towards products.

To be an effective designer, it is important that one can evaluate existing and competing products, whilst also enabling users to express their own meanings towards products. It also highlights how difficult it can be to express experiences and our personal meanings for products. This relates directly to challenges designers face when trying to elicit data from users, holistic rather than specific approaches can help obtain more authentic insight.

The authors are planning a study that will compare and contrast design student emotional responses to a range of products from similar but different cultures. The study will be conducted at Loughborough University (UK) and the University of Illinois (Urbana-Champaign)(USA).

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